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[South Building](#)

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Meeting Resources

Helpful Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Session Catalog• Optional ESDS Events• NASA Hyperwall Science Schedule
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Monday, Dec 12, 2022

(All times central)

8:00 AM - 12:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Open Science Practices and Success Stories Poster Hall - A (South Building)
12:45 - 1:45 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• NASA Planetary Science Division Town Hall McCormick Place - S102cd (South, Level 1)
2:45 - 4:15 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Open Science Practices and Success Stories Oral Part 1 - N426c• 2:50-3:00 - Citizen Science is Open Science: Three Examples from NASA Citizen Science Projects
3:00 PM - 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• TOPS at NASA Booth - NASA Booth #1937

5:50 - 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Science Discovery Engine: An Open Science Success Story - McCormick Place N426c (North, Level 4)
6:30 - 7:30 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA (HPD) Living with a Star Town Hall S102a
6:30 - 7:30 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and Open Science for Capable Communities and Scientific Discovery S104a
6:30 - 9:30 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Earth Science Women Network (ESWN) Reception Hyatt Regency McCormick Place, Room Regency DE

Tuesday, Dec 13, 2022

9:00 AM - 12:30 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA Openscapes: Lessons Learned supporting Cross-DAAC User Services to migrate to the Cloud • A Python Package to Search and Access NASA Earth Science Data (Openscapes) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Poster Hall, Hall A (South, Level 3)
9:30 AM - 10:30 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science Discussion Sessions - AGU Pod 5
10:00 AM - 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TOPS at NASA Booth - NASA Booth #1937
12:45 PM - 1:45 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling the Use of Earth Observations for Equity and Environmental Justice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ McCormick Place - S106a
5:45 PM - 7:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TOPS Community Happy Hour - Location TBD

Wednesday, Dec 14, 2022

10:00 AM - 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA TOPS at NASA Booth - NASA Booth #1937
12:45 - 1:45 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA Open Science Events, Curricula, and Opportunities S103cd
4:05 - 4:20 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA TOPS Hyperwall Talk

6:30 - 7:30 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA SMD Open-Source Science Initiative Town Hall S103cd • Diversity, Inclusion, and Equity in Informatics S102ab
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Thursday, Dec 15, 2022

9:00 AM - 12:30 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowering Open Science Collaboration by Leveraging Spatial Data Infrastructure and Open Data II Poster (Stinger) - McCormick Place - Poster Hall, Hall A (South, Level 3)
10:10 - 11:10 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science Discovery Engine Hyperwall Talk - NASA Booth
12:45-1:45 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA Earth Science Division Town Hall S102ab • Open Science Realities: How Open is Open? S103cd
2:00 PM - 3:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science Discussion Sessions - AGU Pod 5

Friday, Dec 16, 2022

9:00 - 10:30 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Future is Open Innovation (TOPS) Grand Ballroom S100 (South, Level 1)
10:00 AM - 1:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TOPS at NASA Booth - NASA Booth #1937
2:45 - 3:15 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGU-EGU-JpGU Great Debate: Open Science, Societies, and Society - N427A-D

Map and Facility Details

South Building

Level 5

Meeting Rooms
(S501 - S505)

Level 4

Vista Ballroom (S406)
Meeting Rooms (S401-405)

Level 3

Exhibition Halls
Grand Concourse
Sky Bridge to Lakeside Center

Level 2.5

VIP Conference Room
Business Center
Food Court/Restaurant
Shops & Services
First Aid
Mamava Lactation Suite
Metra Trains

Level 1

Grand Ballroom (S100)
Meeting Rooms (S101 - S106)
Gates 1 -4
East Transportation Center (Gates 25 - 27)
Hotel Access
Sky Bridge to West Building

North Building

Level 3 →
Exhibition Halls
Grand Concourse
Sky Bridge to
Lakeside Center

Level 2 →
Meeting Rooms (N226 - N231)
Food Service

Level 1 →
Exhibition Halls
Meeting Rooms (N126 - N140)
Security Command Center
Gates 20 - 22

Level 4
Meeting Rooms
(N426 - N427)

